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Artificial Intelligence and Counselling Techniques in the Contemporary Church in Nigeria

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Abstract

The advent of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is reshaping various sectors globally, and the contemporary Church in Nigeria is no exception. This position paper examines the impact of AI on the Nigerian Church, focusing on its influence on worship practices, pastoral care, counselling techniques and the overall religious experience. Also, the study determines the influence of AI on religious evangelism. The discourse adopts computational learning theory. As churches increasingly adopt AI-driven tools—such as virtual assistants, automated sermon generation, and digital evangelism platforms—the traditional modes of religious expression are being transformed. While AI offers opportunities for broader outreach and personalized spiritual engagement, it also raises ethical concerns about the authenticity of religious experiences and the potential for technological dependency. The study explores how Nigerian churches are navigating these challenges, balancing innovation with doctrinal integrity, and what this means for the future of religion in a technologically advanced society. Through a combination of qualitative analysis and case studies, this research provides insights into the evolving relationship between AI and faith in Nigeria. The connection of tools and faith will boost counselling practices within the church for evangelism work. The study recommends that every church that integrates AI in their church missionary work should be able to enjoy its potentials and be accountable for its shortcomings.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Church, Counselling Techniques, Chatbots

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming various sectors globally, and the religious sphere, particularly the contemporary Church in Nigeria, is no exception. As technology continues to evolve, the integration of AI into the church's operations, mission, and evangelization efforts is becoming increasingly relevant. According to Copeland (2024), artificial intelligence (AI) encompasses the capacity of machines to perform tasks traditionally associated with human rationality and intelligence.

Perez-Cerrolaza, et al. (2024) emphasize that AI operations span various domains, including game playing, language translation, expert systems, and robotics. They further note that while the concept of machines imitating intelligence has ancient roots, the advent of authentic machine intelligence became feasible with the evolution of digital computers in the 1940s. Today, AI has progressed beyond initial projects like chess-playing and mathematical problem-solving, tackling more complex tasks such as visual pattern recognition, intricate decision-making, and natural language processing. The application of Artificial Intelligence in this regard has already proved efficient in several corporate institutions and facilities like technology, banking, marketing, and the entertainment world. Artificial Intelligence thus is everywhere. It has actually come to stay with multidimensional future prospects.

Afunugo and Molokwu (2024) assert that if Jesus Christ were to come to save mankind in this age, He might not ride into Jerusalem on an ass again. He will have to make use of the available cheapest means of transportation to still signify humility and prudence. Truth remains that mankind ought to make use of scientific innovations of which God is the one that endows human kind with such creative capacity and inspiration. The Holy Spirit always ministers to human kind from the known to the unknown. He utilizes things available to man while instructing him.

It will be good that church missionary enterprise in contemporary times especially in Nigeria, should integrate the capabilities and services of Artificial Intelligence in evangelization. Although Lynch (2013) cautions that, human contact, which is exemplified in one-to-one encounter is extremely important and irreplaceable in the church missions. He stresses that even Jesus Christ maintained more of person to person contact in his ministry. Jesus actually trained his 12 Apostles via personal contact; none was operating from afar. Lynch insists that dependence on new technologies can strip that from the church missions. He emphasizes that the question of how the Church can integrate new technologies in the furtherance of her mission ought to be a secondary one.

Thus, there is need for sitting new technologies in order to retain and prioritize on good innovations; and that no technical progress can replace or out-date the level of relationship built by Jesus' kind of communication that hinged on singular, specific, and personal love for His disciples. Lynch (2013) further exposit that church missionaries must embrace man's limitation in their endeavours in order to avert the quest to reach out to a wider audience or congregation thereby dispersing in activity and bearing little fruit in the process. It is actually within the limitations of nature that church missionaries can experience the fulfillment and beauty of their vocation.

The rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) presents both opportunities and challenges for various sectors, including religious institutions. In the context of the Nigerian church, there is a growing interest in leveraging AI to enhance evangelization, improve communication, and manage church operations. However, the integration of AI into church activities is still in its infancy, and its potential impact remains largely unexplored.

The problem lies in understanding how AI can be effectively utilized to support the mission of the Church in Nigeria, particularly in reaching diverse and culturally varied communities. There are concerns about whether AI can accurately interpret and convey religious messages that resonate with the local context, and how it can address the unique challenges faced by the Church, such as language diversity and cultural nuances. Moreover, there is need to assess the ethical implications of AI's use in religious settings, ensuring that the technology aligns with the church's values and mission. This paper specifically is aimed at investigating the impact of AI and counselling techniques on the contemporary churches in Nigeria.

Theoretical framework

The theory adopted for this study is computational learning theory. This study adopts it because it provides a mathematical framework for quantifying learning tasks and algorithms, which are essential in programming artificial intelligence. This theory plays a crucial role in AI, serving as cornerstone of the field. Brownlee (2020) notes that computational learning theory, also known as statistical learning theory or COLT, is concerned with the application of formal mathematical methods to learning systems.

Brownlee (2020) explains that the theory seeks to use theoretical computer science tools to quantify learning problems, including characterizing the difficulty of specific learning tasks. The theory extends or relates to statistical learning theory (SLT) by employing formal techniques to measure and assess the effectiveness of learning algorithms.

Muhammad and Yan (2015) assert that it often focuses on supervised learning, particularly binary classification tasks and simple rule-based systems. However, they also acknowledge that applying

theoretical findings to real-world algorithms and problems can be challenging due to the complexity involved, which limits the practical application and interpretation of the theorems.

The Lark Editorial Team (2023) opinionated that computational learning theory is the foundational framework within AI that explores how machines learn from data, develop algorithms, and make decisions. They highlight its importance in enhancing knowledge acquisition and decision-making abilities in AI systems, making it essential for various advanced technologies. The Lark Editorial Team (2023) further notes that computational learning theory emerged alongside early AI research, coinciding with the development of neural networks and pattern recognition theories. They state further that computational learning theory has evolved with advancements in computing power, algorithms, and data accessibility, making it highly relevant in contemporary AI applications. Thus, making it a fundamental aspect of AI which empowers learning algorithms, predicting modeling and autonomous decision-making. This underscores the pivotal significance within AI, particularly in applications like recommendation systems, natural language processing, and computer vision, which have revolutionized technological capabilities.

Computational learning theory is applicable to this study because it can support the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in evangelization within the Nigerian church mission by providing insights into how AI algorithms can be trained to understand and interpret religious texts, cultural nuances, and local languages. This understanding can aid in developing AI-powered tools such as Chabot or recommendation systems tailored to effectively communicate religious teachings and messages to diverse Nigerian communities.

Additionally, computational learning theory can assist in optimizing the performance of these AI systems through continuous learning and adaptation based on user interactions and feedback, enhancing their effectiveness in spreading the church's message.

Impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on Contemporary Churches

The impact of AI on the contemporary church can be multifaceted, touching on the Church's various ministries, ethics, communication mediums and theology.

- 1. *Enhancing Evangelization Efforts:*** This is perhaps one of the most beneficial effects of AI on the Nigerian church since evangelization forms one of the primary goals of the Church. There is also the possibility to use such AI mechanisms as Chatbots, virtual assistants, or social media algorithms that would expand the circle of the church's influence. They can be set to post the scriptures, answer any questions related to theology or even set people on the right path spiritually. This offers immediate support and resources. While majority of the Nigeria populace is now connected to the internet and social media platforms, the application of AI will enhance the church's desire to spread the word easier and faster. For instance, it can be used to predict or foresee when to put posts on social media so that maximum number of people will view the messages. Further, AI can assist churches to produce the content that will be relevant to their congregation in a way that will lead to answering the questions and concerns people may have, thus having a higher level of spiritual connectedness.
- 2. *Improving Administrative Efficiency:*** AI is also advancing the secretarial operations of the Church to the next level. The regular processes like managing of appointments of the services and the donations, and also the ways of interaction between the leaders of the church and the parishioners, have been improved by the help of the AI for many aspects that were impossible before. This relieves church leaders who often spend most of their time on the management of the church and giving of spiritual directions. AI tools can also be used in proper coordination of the resources that are available in the church. For instance, when it comes to church services, the usual turnout of congregation can be predicted using predictive analytics thus helping in correct rationing of resources, identify at-risk individuals and provide proactive support. It also fortifies the organizational structure of the church and the experience of the congregation is also enriched.

Ethical and Theological Considerations:

The benefits of AI in the Church are evident. However, this raises significant ethical and theological questions.

1. The use of AI in religious contexts challenges traditional notions of spirituality, human agency, and the role of the church. For instance, Chatbots can provide the same level of spiritual guidance as a human pastor? How does the use of AI in decision-making processes affect the church's commitment to divine inspiration and human discernment? These are critical questions that the contemporary church in Nigeria must address as it navigates the integration of AI. It is essential to develop a theological framework that guides the use of AI in ways that align with Christian values and principles. AI can analyze emotions and concerns in prayer requests or counselling sessions. Through counselling techniques on the part of the ministers, the church will not only understand the capabilities and limitations of AI but also discerning the ways in which AI can complement, rather than replace, human roles in the church.
2. Automation of Administrative tasks: AI can be employed to streamline operations within the Church's administrative structure. For instance, tools such as Chatbots can be employed to answer inquiries from members, programmed to send reminders about church's upcoming programme and as well as the use of a bill board with evangelistic messages. It can suggest relevant scriptures, prayers, or resources. However, this cannot replace the role of the Holy Spirit in Spiritual matters.

Influence of Artificial intelligence (AI) on Evangelism

Lang (2024) advocates the use of AI tools as being powerful. Musonda (2023) suggests some beneficial ways AI can be used for evangelism:

1. **Repurposing Sermons with AI Tools:** This involves using AI to adapt and refine sermons for different platforms and audiences such as different languages to meet up with cultural diversity.
2. **Using AI to generate Audience-Capturing Images during sermons:** AI can create visuals that resonate with the congregation during sermons.
3. **Creating Engaging Social Media Posts:** AI can design visually appealing social media content to attract and engage audiences.
4. **AI in Newsletter Preparation:** AI can be utilized to craft well-structured and informative newsletters.
5. **Increase accessibility:** AI helps to have access to large numbers of converts and members
6. **Enhanced efficiency:** AI makes evangelism more productive, reaching diverse cultures

Some challenges were highlighted below:

1. **Data Privacy and Security:** information is generalized, open to general public
2. **Limited Human Interaction:** AI makes interaction among members to reduce drastically
3. **Potential Biases in AI Algorithms:** there are biases in some quarters due to unacceptability of AI
4. **Theological and Ethical considerations:** consideration of ethical consideration by different theology schools can be a barrier to the use of AI

Zhang and Zhang (2020) conclude by emphasizing that if AI is to be used appropriately, it must respect individuals' privacy and autonomy. He points out that certain AI techniques might be considered inappropriate in a diverse nation like Nigeria, with its various tribal, linguistic, and religious complexities. Musonda (2023) further asserts that with proper programming, training, design, and testing, AI can be unbiased and free of defects. He stresses the importance of ensuring that the data and algorithms used are accurate and unbiased, which is crucial for the smooth, trustworthy, and reliable operation of AI.

Chabata (2024) on his part argues that the scriptures do not prohibit Christians from using AI. He believes that AI can be an effective tool for spreading the gospel in modern society. From his analysis, it is evident

that any church using platforms like YouTube, Google, or Facebook is already engaging with AI in some form. He advises that AI should be applied in a manner that aligns with biblical principles, and care should be taken to avoid using it in ways that could harm others or invade their privacy, major reason why counselling techniques is needed among the ministers and members of the church especially in rural areas. Musonda (2023) further states that AI has the potential to revolutionize various aspects of life, including church missionary work, as AI becomes increasingly integrated into society. He highlights that AI-powered Chabot's can assist in answering questions about Christianity, providing biblical references, and engaging in faith-based conversations. Musonda notes that AI makes it easier to evangelize densely populated areas by analyzing data from social media and surveys to understand the audience's struggles and challenges. With this information, AI can help craft messages tailored to the audience's needs, which is particularly effective in Nigeria, where addressing people's specific needs and concerns is crucial.

However, Youvan (2024) also emphasizes that while AI can provide valuable information and resources, it cannot replace the divine inspiration that comes from God. The God Kulture Team in the year 2023 adds that AI can assist in evangelism by repurposing sermons. They point out that in today's fast-paced world, not everyone has the time or attention span to engage with lengthy YouTube sermons. AI can help the church condense and adapt sermons for various platforms, converting them into text for blogs or creating bite-sized social media posts. This approach is highly relevant in Nigeria, where social media content creation and news blogging are widespread and popular.

La Cruz and Mora (2024) suggest that evangelical and Pentecostal cum Charismatic Churches (EPCCS) employ advanced AI tools to improve the sanctification process for believers; in translating the Bible, distributing and fostering its reading around the world; and the spreading of spiritual revival among EPCCS through mediated algorithms. They express that there are clear future positive prospects pertinent to the integration of AI in the church missionary enterprise.

Integrating AI for Evangelization in Nigeria: Socio Religious Approaches

Several socio-religious considerations are essential when incorporating AI for effective evangelization in Nigerian Church. It is vital to ensure that the use of AI in evangelism aligns with the cultural norms, values, and customs of the Nigerian society. Messages delivered through AI should be culturally sensitive and respectful to avoid causing offense, confusion, or misunderstanding, especially in a multi-ethnic, tribal, and linguistically diverse nation like Nigeria.

When using AI for evangelism in Nigeria, it is crucial to ensure that messages are consistent with Christian teachings and beliefs, engaging effectively with the target audience. This should be done without making derogatory or offensive remarks about other religious groups. Additionally, the acceptance of AI in evangelism may differ among various Christian denominations. Therefore, an ecumenical public awareness campaign highlighting the benefits and significance of AI for evangelization in the Nigerian church mission is necessary to facilitate broad acceptance.

Churches must ensure that an AI-generated content for evangelism is truthful, accurate, respectful, and culturally appropriate. Data privacy should be maintained, and individuals or groups should not be manipulated through targeted messaging. Establishing ethical guidelines and ensuring transparency in AI usage for evangelism is essential to maintain trust and credibility.

AI-generated messages should therefore promote peace, unity, and solidarity within Nigeria. Evangelical content shared via AI should encourage citizens to actively participate in nation-building and fulfill their civic responsibilities. It is also crucial to involve local communities in the design and implementation of AI-driven evangelism initiatives to ensure their relevance and effectiveness. AI should never be used to promote parallel governance or incite insubordination against the government.

The effectiveness of utilizing AI for evangelization in Nigeria will depend on various factors, including the quality of the content, audience engagement, and the alignment of AI tools with community values and beliefs. Churches using AI for evangelization should continuously assess and adjust their strategies to ensure positive impacts and meaningful connections with their target audience.

Counselling Techniques

Clergy can make use of the following counselling techniques to facilitate AI in church evangelism.

1. **Narrative Therapy:** This enables leaders and members to reframe their stories in positive patterns. The clergy and leaders can use prospective storytelling which will enable them to formulate a joint medium and long-term vision, mission and a corresponding action plan with the members. It is in particular seeks to empower groups and individuals with provisions of resources and skills needed for positively improving the well being and coping with a wide range of life challenges (Madigan, 2011).
2. **Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT):** Beck (2020) developed this technique in year 1960s. These addresses thought patterns and behaviours of an individual clergy. CBT is a psychotherapy that aims to assist members with emotional and personality disorders which are caused by faulty thinking. The clergy and leaders of the church use verbal and intellectual techniques to assist the members to identify and change the dysfunctional beliefs and thought processes (Rachman, 2015).
3. **Solution-Focused Brief Therapy (SFBT):** This therapy helps individual see solutions rather than problems of AI to evangelism. SFBT is the best way to see members through difficulties in order for them to regain hope and be faithful to God's call (Griffiths, 2023).
4. **Spiritual Direction:** This explores spiritual growth and faith development of individual church members toward integration of AI. It is the practice of being with members as they attempt to deepen their relationship with the divine, or learning and growing in their personal spirituality. The clergy or leader seeking direction always shares stories of their experiences of the divine or how they are taming a life in tune to spiritual things (Evans, 2015).

Counselling Implications

The intersection of technology and faith can enhance counselling practices within the Church. Family issues such as marriage issues between spouses, conflicts that people have with others, health issues, issues with children and financial issues which are among the most common issues that members brought to church for counselling. The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in counselling has opened new avenues for enhancing the effectiveness and reach of mental health services. The church can explore the potential of AI to augment the counselling process by automating administrative tasks, providing data-driven insights, and offering additional resources for therapeutic interventions in the church and the work of evangelism. The advancements and introduction of AI bring about a balanced approach that combines human empathy and AI efficiency. The study emphasizes the importance of human-AI collaboration, where AI serves as a tool to empower individuals and achieve their wellness goals while maintaining the core values of the church doctrine. The advancements of AI enhance the gospel rather than replacing the essential human element in church ministry.

The clergy will adopt the right counselling practices such as listening, adhering to ethical issues, utilizing counselling skills, confrontational, assertiveness, availability and building strong relationships with members. Lack of resources and time as well as inadequacy on the part of clergy will be taken care of by AI and chatbots.

Conclusion

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into evangelization within the Nigerian church missions presents significant opportunities for enhancing outreach, communication, and engagement. However, it also introduces complex challenges that must be carefully addressed to ensure its effectiveness and ethical application. AI offers powerful tools that can be leveraged to reach diverse audiences, adapt messages to local cultural and linguistic contexts, and support church operations in a rapidly changing digital landscape. When used appropriately, AI can help churches in Nigeria deliver the gospel more effectively, tailor messages to the specific needs and concerns of different communities, and maintain a consistent presence across various digital platforms.

However, the successful implementation of AI in evangelization requires careful consideration of several socio-religious factors, including cultural awareness, religious tolerance, ethical standards, community involvement, and the need for human empathy in ministry. It is essential to ensure that AI-driven initiatives respect the cultural and religious diversities of Nigeria, uphold the core values of the Christian faith, and engage with communities in a way that promotes peace, unity, and nation-building.

Moreover, the challenges related to the literacy levels of the target audience, the availability of resources, and the potential for AI to depersonalize the message of the gospel must be addressed. Churches must strike a balance between leveraging the efficiency of AI while preserving the human race that is central to effective ministry. In conclusion, AI has the potential to revolutionize evangelization in Nigeria, but its integration must be approached with caution, sensitivity, and a commitment to ethical principles. By ensuring that AI is used responsibly and in alignment with the church's mission, Nigerian churches can harness the power of technology to expand their outreach and maintaining the integrity and authenticity of their message. AI is not to take the place of men but to complement the work of ministry.

Suggestions

The following suggestions were made:

1. Every church that integrates Artificial Intelligence in their church missionary work should be accountable for its shortcomings. This should make those churches to leave no stone unturned in the programming of their AI Robotics perfectly.
2. Nigerian government should capitalize on furnishing Federal Universities in the country with the necessary equipment and tools for Artificial Intelligence Robotics and Algorithms studies.
3. To organize workshops and seminars in order to create awareness and educate church leaders and members about the importance of AI in enhancing church missions and reaching wider audience by those at the helm of authorities of Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN).
4. Churches in Nigeria should foster partnerships with AI organizations to develop tailored ideas of spreading the gospel, such as AI-powered chat-bots for answering spiritual questions or AI-driven content recommendation systems for personalized outreach.
5. The Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) should establish ethical guidelines for the use of AI in religious contexts to ensure that its deployment aligns with the values and principles of the church.
6. Church denominations in Nigeria should offer training programs for clergy and volunteers on how to effectively utilize AI tools in their outreach efforts.
7. If there is a lack of human capacity in this area, individuals should be trained in AI for church missions in Nigeria. Any biases and idiosyncrasies must be avoided, with a focus on achieving practical evangelization through the combined efforts of both human and technology.

8. Counselling techniques and skills should be employed by church leadership as this will enhance their ministry and care for their congregation. AI driven tools would provide access to counselling on the go 24/7 outside the traditional office hours.

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